

Theoretical calculation of Activation Energy for the addition of Bromine to Ethylene using different Potential Energy Functions.

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Different potential energy functions were tested for the calculation of activation energy for the addition of bromine to ethylene by Eyring's semi-empirical method. Rydberg's function has been found to give the best result.

Since Eyring and Polanyi gave a quantum mechanical description of transition state in a chemical reaction, various attempts²⁻⁴ have been made from time to time to make an abinitio calculation of activation energy of bimolecular reaction. The latest attempt by Bowen and Linnett⁵ using a high speed computer has shown that even for simple reaction like $H_2 + H = H + H_2$, the absolute energy calculation is so heavy that it is fairly certain that no such calculation can be made on any system of chemical interest in foreseeable future. This does not mean that no energy calculation is possible on complex systems. The semi-empirical methods of calculations which have been attended with spectacular success on the- π -electron system of conjugated organic molecule suggests that some progress is possible, with the semi-empirical calculation of activation energy of various chemical reactions. By semi-empirical method is meant an exact formulation of quantum mechanical problems but evaluation of various molecular integrals from the experimental data on molecular spectroscopy. One such method is due to Eyring and co-workers where only the electrons involved in the chemical reactions are considered explicitly and the coulomb and exchange integrals are evaluated from the potential energy diagram of diatomic systems, in the activated complex, constructed from Infra-red and Raman Spectral data. The potential energy function that has been almost exclusively used to fit Infra-red data in these type of calculations is in the one due to Morse. The Morse function has an analytical form and is simple to use. That is practically the only qualification for Morse function. It is already well established that this function over estimates all spectral quantities like dissociation energy, anharmonicity constant, equilibrium internuclear distance etc. Spectroscopists have suggested various

1. H. Eyring and M. Polanyi, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **12 B**, 279.
2. J. Hirschfelder, H. Eyring and N. Rosen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, **4**, 121.
3. S. F. Boys and I. Shavitt, Wisconsin Technical Report WIS—AF-13, 4 March, 1959.
4. H. Conroy and B. L. Bruner, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 4047.
5. H. C. Bowen and J. W. Linnett, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 2953.

modifications for Morse function that reproduces the experimental molecular quantities better. The object of the present investigation was to use potential functions due to Morse, Rydberg, Lippincot and Hirschfelder et al, in the calculation of activation energy for addition of bromine to ethylene.

The method of constructing the potential energy surfaces has been described in detail in a previous communication⁶. Fig. 1 shows the geometry at the transition state for the addition of bromine to ethylene. The potential energy surfaces constructed using various potential energy functions given in the appendix are shown in Fig. 2-5.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the transition state.

Fig. 2. Contour surface using Morse function.

Fig. 3. Contour surface using Rydberg function.

Fig. 4. Contour surface using Lippincot function.

Fig. 5. Contour surface using Hilbert and Hirschfelder function.

The activation energies given by the height of the pass between two valleys are tabulated below :

Potential energy function	Activation energy (K Cal/mole)
Morse function	25
Rydberg function	23
Lippincot function	14
Hilbert & Hirschfelder function	29

The estimated activation energy for this system is 22.6 K Cal/mole⁷. It is evident that best result is obtained with Rydberg function when both contour surface and actual activation energy are considered, although Morse function gives a value of activation energy also close to the experimental one. The result is not unexpected. In the chemical reaction some old bonds are broken and new bonds are formed. The activation process therefore will depend on the strength of the bonds which are broken and are formed. Consequently the activation energy will be governed by the dissociation energy of the bond and the function which correctly reproduces dissociation energy will also give best value for activation energy. It is

7. A. Sherman, Oscar T. Quimby and R. O. Sutherland, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 732.

already well established that Rydberg function gives the best value for dissociation energy at equilibrium intermolecular distance, so it should give best value for the activation energy.

It is to be pointed out that the calculation refers to gas phase reaction. In condensed state where potential energy curve is altered due to environmental perturbation, the function which reflects this effect, correctly reproduces anharmonicity of the interaction, will be more useful in activation energy calculation.

A P P E N D I X

The different potential energy functions tested are given as below :

Morse function :

$$V(r) = D_e \left[e^{-2a(r-r_e)} - 2e^{-a(r-r_e)} \right]$$

where D_e is the dissociation energy plus the zero point energy and a is a constant for a given molecular electronic state.

Rydberg function :

$$V(r) = -D_e \left[1 + b(r-r_e) e^{-b(r-r_e)} \right]$$

where D_e is the dissociation energy plus the zero point energy and b is a constant for given state.

Lippincot function :

$$V(r) = D_e \left[1 - e^{-n(r-r_e)^2/2r} \right] - D_e$$

where n is a constant.

Hilburt and Hirschfelder function :

$$V(r) = D_e \left[\left(1 - e^{-x} \right)^2 + Cx^3 e^{-2x} (1 + bx) \right] - D_e$$

where $x = a(r-r_e)$, a being the Morse function constant and b and c are other constants.

These constants can be derived by the well-known method⁸. Molecular constants used in the construction of these curves are given below :

Bond constants for different potential energy curves.

Bond	r_e (Å)	W_e (Cm ⁻¹)	D (K Cal/mole)
C—C	1.46	—	61.0
C—Br	2.06	560	58.0
Br—Br	2.28	323.86	45.23

The reaction path of the addition of bromine to ethylene, will be clearly visualized if we plot the contour surface along a screw axis as is shown by Eyring. Fig. 6 shows such a contour surface where the energy is plotted along the screw

Fig. 6. Contour surface using Rydberg function along screw axis.

axes r_1 , and r_2 . The reaction path is shown along the dotted line BOA. The two bromine atoms vibrate along PQ, the dotted line. As they come at the point O, during vibration they meet a downhill potential slope so they proceed along OA and the vibration is converted into translation. Similarly the reverse path will bring about the dissociation of ethyl-bromide into ethylene and bromine due to conversion of C-Br vibration into a translation.